

CERTIFICATION IN BRANDING NATURAL PASTURE MEAT

1. Grazing cattle in Finland 2. Forest pasture in Southern Finland 3. Forest pasture in Eastern Finland 4. Grazing sheep in Finland (Photos: Tanja Kähkönen)

WHAT AND WHY

Certification is one way to brand, to create an image of agroforestry products and services for consumers. Certification increases transparency of meat production practices from farmers to consumers, particularly regarding impacts of food production on the environment and biodiversity. It also shows the origin of the meat. Natural pasture meat is derived from animals which graze on natural or semi-natural pastures, including traditional rural biotopes such as wood pastures and meadows in Finland, environments shaped by traditional livestock herding over centuries.

Whereas in the past natural and semi-natural pastures were important livestock grazing areas as a part of traditional agriculture, nowadays only a fraction of them is left. Many of these areas receive government support for managing traditional rural habitats. As a result, the abundance of insects and plants dependent on grazing has declined leading to changes in biodiversity in these landscapes. Currently about one fourth of endangered species in Finland live in natural and semi-natural pastures and need them as their habitats.

Keywords: Branding, certification, marketing

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

The first Finnish farm received natural pasture meat certification in 2022. Meat with grazing on natural and semi-natural pastures has been produced in Finland also before this and continues to be produced also without certification. However, the certification verifies for the consumer that natural pasture meat certification criteria such as animals grazing on natural pastures for at least 50% of the grazing period are met. Compliance to the certification criteria is monitored by farm audits and regular reporting. Finnish natural pasture meat certification was inspired by similar certification in Sweden.

Besides certification of natural pasture meat, "national natural pasture day" an event where farmers have an open day at their farm has been arranged since 2022 to promote natural pasture grazing among consumers.

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ADVANTAGES

Certification supports consumers to make informed decisions on meat consumption. In the case of natural pasture meat certification this means that consumers know that the minimum share of how much animals graze on natural pastures during grazing period and how they are fed during housing period. Essentially through certification consumers receive information on these topics affecting animal wellbeing. At the same time, consumers can be assured of environmental aspects of natural pasture meat. The environmental aspects are not necessarily mentioned in certification criteria but a direct or indirect result of grazing on natural and semi-natural pastures with benefits for the ecosystem.

Grazing on natural and semi-natural pastures is one of the few food production methods which have potential to increase biodiversity. While grazing changes plant community by reducing nutrients and very abundant plant species, it creates space for more rare species and those dependent on grazing. In addition, the manure of the animals supports biodiversity by creating habitats for species dependent on it. Continuous plant cover in grazed areas prevents nutrients leaching to water bodies and supports carbon binding in the soil. As there is no need for fertilization or soil preparation, the associated carbon dioxide emissions are avoided.

Grazing prevents encroachment of traditional rural habitats which supports both biodiversity and landscape values. Without grazing, traditional rural habitats and their biodiversity would continue disappearing. Through choosing natural pasture meat over conventionally produced meat, consumers support nature management and maintenance of traditional rural habitats by grazing.

Grazing on natural and semi-natural pastures can reduce cultivation pressure on arable land as animals feed on plants growing on natural and semi-natural pastures and they are not fully dependent on crops produced on arable land. Areas that would not otherwise be available for crop production may be utilised for grazing creating even less pressure on arable land for other agricultural purposes.

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HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Certification is one way to brand, to create an image of agroforestry to consumers.**
- **Certification increases transparency of meat production practices from farmers to consumers and supports consumers to make informed decisions.**
- **Branding agroforestry products through certification makes the benefits of agroforestry more visible to consumers.**

Traditional rural habitat grazed by sheep in Eastern Finland. (Photo:Tanja Kähkönen)

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